

Excercising Power Through Coercion and Co-Opting

Dr. Hanna-e-Kalbi

Dept. of Humanities, University of Management and Technology, Lahore

Wajeeha Ilyas

Dept. Of Humanities, COMSATS University Islamabad, Islamabad

Dr. Sadia Siddiq

Dept. Of Humanities, COMSATS University Islamabad, Islamabad

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
213-229

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Volume:3, Issue:2, 2023

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

OJS **PKP**
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Abstract

Power is a complex and controversial concept in international relations, categorized into hard power and soft power. Hard power involves military force and coercion through economic rewards or sanctions, while soft power focuses on cultural and ideological attraction to promote a country's foreign policy priorities. The effective use of power requires a nuanced understanding of how these forms interact, with hard power historically being the dominant form. In today's globalized and interconnected world, soft power is increasingly important. A thoughtful and strategic approach relying on persuasion and non-coercive measures is necessary to co-opt others to share values, goals, and agendas. Soft power has been instrumental in advancing US foreign policy objectives, with economic sanctions being a key example. However, a simplistic understanding of soft power and reliance on one form over another can be misguided and counter-productive. A balanced approach to using both hard and soft power strategies in international relations is essential, and this research would be useful for policymakers and scholars seeking to understand the complexities of power in international relations and guide their approach to diplomacy and foreign policy.

Keywords: Hard Power; Soft Power; Diplomacy, Politics, Coercion.

Corresponding Author Email:

hanna.kalbi@umt.edu.pk